

ENGINEERING STUDENTS' MOTIVATION FOR LEARNING IN CHALLENGE-DRIVEN PROJECT COURSES: A QUALITATIVE PILOT STUDY

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ABSTRACT

This pilot study explores engineering students' motivation for learning and studying through the lens of Self-Determination Theory (SDT). Five postgraduate students from a research-intensive Swedish university participated in semi-structured qualitative interviews about their study experiences from different Challenge-Driven Education (CDE) courses. It adds to the limited, existing literature on CDE and is the first to study it from a purely motivational perspective. As this is a pilot study, the primary intent of the data analysis concerns the first two phases of Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis approach - familiarisation and immersion in the data and generating initial codes. A combination of inductive and deductive approaches to analysing the data were used, and preliminary motivational factors emerged from the interviews are illustrated according to the SDT concepts. A variety of motivations for learning and studying, such as innovation, real-world problem solving, contribution to the society, and trial for following master thesis projects, emerged from the data and positioned on the self-determination continuum in which different types of regulations are guiding students' behaviours simultaneously. Furthermore, autonomy in the choice of a project, feedback and assignment deadlines, and relationships within group work, enhanced or/and undermined the three psychological needs defined by SDT; autonomy, competence and relatedness. Preliminary findings are discussed in relation to the SDT literature, and practical applications are suggested for supporting the motivational needs of engineering students. Finally plans for a continuation of the study are discussed in light of this initial phase.

1 INTRODUCTION

There is emerging interest in learning approaches where students are collaboratively engaged across disciplines in open-ended projects that concerns complex real-world issues and interaction with various external stakeholders. Such learning approaches can for example be referred to as challenge-driven education 'CDE', challenge-based learning 'CBL, or problem- and project-based learning 'PPBL (e.g. [1], [2]). There have been attempts made to define some of these concepts (e.g. [3]), still there are large differences in how each of these concepts are being interpreted and implemented (e.g. [4]). There are also many implementations of such learning approaches that are not explicitly associated with any of these terms and concepts. These differences and the lack of definitional clarity do however not pose any barriers to exploring features and key concerns that these learning approaches have in common. One such feature is the opportunity in these learning approaches to enhance students' motivation for studying and learning.

In this pilot study, self-determination theory (SDT) [5]&[6] is used as a lens for exploring factors that facilitate or undermine the motivation for studying and learning among students engaged in these kinds of learning approaches (for simplicity hereafter referred to as challenge-driven education, CDE). A qualitative methodology has been used to investigate the following research questions:

- (a) What are the motivational factors that guide students engaged in CDE?
- (b) How do they relate to the SDT self-determination continuum?

(c) How are the needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness, as defined by SDT, experienced and fulfilled among engineering students engaged in CDE?

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Participants

Five students in three different CDE courses were engaged on voluntary basis as a response to an invitation to participate in this study; three students in a course named Innovations for *Emerging Cities*, one student in the course *Ergonomics in Challenge-Driven Product Development*, and one student in the course *Innovation and Product Development*. The small number of participants is of course a limitation not allowing for data saturation. It should however be noticed that this is a pilot study with the purpose of enabling the researcher to practise the interviewing techniques and investigate the appropriateness of the interview questions as preparation a larger following main study.

2.2 Study design and Data analysis

Semi-structured interviews were constructed, conducted and analyzed in conformity with two methodological approaches: (1) thematic analysis, providing an inductive process, coding the content of the data in order to reveal emerging themes [7]. Specifically, the first two phases of Braun and Clark's [8] thematic analysis approach followed: (a) reading and familiarisation of the data; (b) taking note of items of potential interest which seemed relevant to the research questions; (c) coding; (2) theory-driven analysis [9], analyzing the data in a deductive process, relating the content to SDT concepts, observing arguments with SDT, enhanced by remarkable aspects portrayed by the pilot study's participants. The design of the interview protocol is informed by these approaches, which included both general questions regarding learning and studying motivation and specific questions relating to SDT constructs.

2.3 Interviews

In this pilot study, the coordination of the recruitment process was held by the first author and a co-author, four interviews were carried out by the first author, and one interview was conducted by both the first author and a co-author to strengthen the trustworthiness. The interviews took place online through Zoom agreed upon with the student. Each online interview lasted approximately 45-60 minutes, and all participants were interviewed in English. All interviews were audio/video recorded and transcribed verbatim for analysis.

3 FINDINGS

Two major categories emerged from the data. The first category gives a preliminary insight to the first research question — what are the motivational factors that guide CBL students in their studies? It focuses on motives that the students argued for studying a CBL course. Subsequently, answering the second research question, four motivational factors were identified and positioned progressively along the self-

determination continuum [5]-[6], from the most extrinsically regulated behavior, to more self-determined behavior. The second category corresponded with the psychological needs described by SDT and with the third research question, examining how the needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness are experienced and fulfilled by engineering students in different CBL courses. The categories and representative quotes are illustrated in Fig. 1.

Autonomy

Enhanced by

- Teachers supported with free choices
- Innovative, progressive, and radical students’ ideas and solutions on the challenge

Undermined by

- Teachers’ decisions to divide the students into groups
- Pre-determined projects from the external stakeholders (challenge givers) / “safe choice”
- Pressure by the ext. stakeholders
- Legitimacy of project rights

Competence

Enhanced by

- Students’ skills, abilities, and previous experience
- Students’ positive performance of projects tasks
- Groups productive feedback
- Teachers’ positive feedback
- External stakeholders’ positive performance feedback and progression of the project
- Optimal challenges / problems solving

Undermined by

- No efficient feedback by the teachers and stakeholders (workload) on time
- Limited data provided to the students by the external stakeholders
- Not well-structured learning environment e.g., assignments/deadlines

Relatedness

Enhanced by

- Students’ group belonging, team work, respect, and caring
- Teachers’ focused engagement on students’ group/collaboration/communication

Undermined by

- Students drop out from the group work and the CBL course
- Students’ conflicts
- No presence of external stakeholders to students’ presentations
- The switch/shift among different teachers during the weekly meetings with students, NOT establishing sense of belonging and communication

Fig. 1. Emerging categories and quotes, positioned along to the self-determination continuum [5]-[6], and in relation to the three psychological needs postulated by SDT

4 DISCUSSION

A variety of motivations for studying a CBL course emerged from the data. Innovation and further collaboration with the external stakeholders were motivations

for studying CBL courses by an entrepreneur student. Additionally, a student who included a CBL course for his studies argued that it would be a good opportunity for doing a Master's thesis in the same company which collaborated with during the course. According to SDT, these externally regulated reasons for studying and learning fit the common definition of introjected regulation, depending on internal rewards of self-esteem for success [6].

Another student argued that the design thinking construct of the CBL course motivated to develop problem-solving skills for addressing societal challenges. The experiences shared demonstrate how design thinking, real world problem-solving skills and values of society are internalized to become intrinsically voice identifying with the value of the CBL course activities as an aim for itself, and thus can be positioned within the category of identified extrinsic regulation.

Last but not least, the contribution to society was a motive for a student who studied a CBL course. This student's behavior was facilitated by interest, enjoyment, and engaging of the challenge, and thus can be positioned within the category of intrinsic motivation.

Students related implicitly to all three psychological needs defined by SDT as particularly fundamental of the motivational process: autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Components of all three needs were mentioned as positive factors when enhanced, and negative factors when these needs were undermined.

With regard to autonomy, it is argued that when students experienced a sense of choice, they felt more autonomous, and facilitated their performance in the project tasks, resulting in an increased intrinsic motivation for studying and learning [6]. Whereas research has shown that, controlling teachers' and external stakeholders' behaviors (e.g., using pre-determined project challenges) are negatively related with students' autonomous motivation [10] and are related to an increased frustration of the basic needs across the educational process, and avoidance of challenges [11].

With regard to competence, students' perceptions are agreed with SDT that according to Niemiec & Ryan [12], students' competence supported by teachers' allowance to them to test and to expand their competences and skills; providing them with appropriate tools and performance feedback; offering optimal challenges that students understand, engage, value, and master; and necessary feedback which downplays evaluation promoting students' effectance, providing guides on how to master the learning tasks at hand. However, the findings agree with previous research that students and teachers' heavy workload on CBL courses negatively affect students' motivation [9]. Furthermore, according to SDT, when external policies of the external stakeholders [13] and teachers' experienced work overload [14] affect the educational process then negatively associated with both teachers' and students' autonomous motivation and perceived competence.

With regard to relatedness, the findings showed that relatedness was enhanced by students' sense of belonging and connection with teachers and external stakeholders, respect, and caring within their groups work, relating to the CBL

courses' construct of team work to encourage them. Relatedness is also highly associated with students' perception of that the teachers genuinely respect and value them, with students besides to internalize and accept as their own the practices and values of those to whom they feel a sense of belonging. Whereas students who experienced a sense of disconnectedness or rejection by teachers or/and other external stakeholders would be argued in this pilot study, are more likely to move away from internalization and intrinsic motivation for learning and continue study [12].

5 CONCLUSIONS

The current pilot study provides a preliminary investigation of students' motivation for learning and studying in different CBL courses. Preliminary findings support the relevance of the SDT framework and lead to practical implications, suggesting not only 'what works' in CBL courses learning practices, but also why certain learning environment adjustments are important, and what motivational needs they serve. All motivational factors that students experienced and presented in this pilot study which undermined the three basic psychological needs should be taken into consideration and eliminated by teachers, CBL educational developers, and external stakeholders. Additionally, all factors that facilitated and enhanced the needs should continue to be flourished in CDE. The included real-world challenges of CDE should continue to bring students 'closer to the real world' [15] increasing motivation and engagement [16] by having an impact on students' lives [17]. However, it also needs to be agreed with the perspective of Ryan and Niemiec [18] that the direction of SDT is to broaden the idea that universities are just about developing skills and competences for some future employment. Instead, in this view they are about developing abilities and attitudes that include enjoyment, curiosity, interest, access to resources and data for transparency, confidence, and empowerment. When universities and teachers embrace such a vision, they can become liberators and help students develop critical thinking they need to use for the transformation of society to be more progressive, productive, and increase human wellness.

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